

Suprafacial Catalysis : Is N₂O Decomposition a Model Reaction ?

G. NAGASUBRAMANIAN and M. V. C. SASTRI

Materials Science Research Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600 036
and

B. VISWANATHAN

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600 036

Manuscript received 28 October 1977, revised 10 April 1978, accepted 2 October 1978

Studies were undertaken on the kinetics of N₂O decomposition on MTiO₃ type meta-titanates in two pressure ranges. At low pressure range (<50 torr) the rate has a first order dependence on the partial pressure of N₂O while that at high pressure range (>200 torr) can be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k P_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} / (P_{\text{O}_2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

To account for the suprafacial nature of the decomposition of N₂O on the above catalysts measurements were made of the changes in Seebeck Potential and electrical conductivity in various ambient atmospheres.

IN any typical oxidation, reduction reactions the catalysts can function in two different ways. In one case it can enter the reaction as a relatively inert template providing a collection of atomic or molecular orbitals of suitable symmetry and energy or in another case, the catalyst can actually participate in the reaction as a reagent being partially consumed or reformed in a continuous cycle. These two extreme cases are designated as 'suprafacial' and 'intrafacial catalysis respectively. Examples of reaction proceeding by intrafacial catalysis involving Mars-van Krevelen type of mechanism (comprising the partial removal of oxygen from the lattice by one reagent) are numerous like the oxidation of olefine, reduction of NO by CO, oxidation of CO etc. The 'intrafacial' catalysis can be established unequivocally by the feasibilities of the studies with isotopic oxygen as well as from the evaluation of the thermodynamics of the reduction-oxidation cycles.

On the other hand examples of reactions proceeding by 'suprafacial' catalysis are sparse and any discussion on suprafacial catalysis must start with

a search for a relationship between the electronic properties of the catalyst and the catalytic activity since for a reaction proceeding by this mechanism the relevant energy levels are those around the Fermi level, i.e., the lowest unoccupied and the highest occupied levels.

N₂O Decomposition and the catalyst taken for study:

The catalysts studied and the rate law observed are discussed elsewhere¹. At low pressure range, namely, <50 torr, the rate has a first order dependence on the pressure of N₂O while at high pressure range, namely, >200 torr the rate can be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k P_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} / (P_{\text{O}_2})^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

After a detailed kinetic study, a mechanism was proposed which will be dealt with in the next section. The relevant electronic properties, studied, are given in Table 1, and the variations observed in electronic properties in various ambient atmospheres are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE-1. ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES OF CATALYSTS USED

Catalyst	Type	Electrical conductivity at 500° (in air) ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Seebeck coefficient at 500° μV/°C	Activation energy for electrical conduction eV
MgTiO ₃	n	5.28 × 10 ⁻³	- 200.00	0.398
MnTiO ₃	n	3.16 × 10 ⁻³	- 142.00	0.560
CoTiO ₃	n	1.50 × 10 ⁻³	-	0.690
NiTiO ₃	n	1.26 × 10 ⁻³	- 125.00	0.790
CaTiO ₃	n	-	-	-
SrTiO ₃	p	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸	-	0.770
BaTiO ₃	p	-	-	0.750
NiO	p	2.57 × 10 ⁻²	+ 160.00	0.154
MgO	-	5.93 × 10 ⁻⁹	-	0.638
TiO ₂	-	1.44 × 10 ⁻⁹	-	0.494

TABLE-2. VARIATION OF ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES IN AMBIENT ATMOSPHERES

Catalyst	Conductivity changes in		Seebeck coefficient changes ($\Delta\alpha$)	
	O ₂ (480°)	N ₂ O(350°)	O ₂ (400°)	N ₂ O(200°)
MgTiO ₃	Negligible decrease	Negligible decrease	Decreases—10 μ V/°C	-
MnTiO ₃	Decreases ($\Delta\sigma=4.46 \times 10^{-3}$)	Decrease ($\Delta\sigma=0.194 \times 10^{-3}$)	Decreases -120 μ V/°C	Decreases -790 μ V/°C
CoTiO ₃	Decreases ($\Delta\sigma=4.20 \times 10^{-3}$)	Decreases ($\Delta\sigma=0.180 \times 10^{-3}$)	-	-
NiTiO ₃	Decreases ($\Delta\sigma=1.05 \times 10^{-5}$)	Decreases ($\Delta\sigma=0.084 \times 10^{-7}$)	Decreases -100 μ V/°C	Decreases -650 μ V/°C

In the case of these ternary oxides the electronic structure is mainly determined by the 3d levels of the cations and the *p*-orbitals of the oxygen. A detailed discussion of the electronic structure of the MTiO₃ type oxides is given by Goodenough².

Mechanism of N₂O decomposition :

The reaction mechanism for the decomposition which can account for all the observed result is⁸

In this sequence the adsorption of N₂O molecule in the reactive form as N₂O⁻ requires the presence of anion vacancies, that is F-centres, or the molecule should acquire the required electron by surface migration. The charged adsorbed complex decomposes giving rise to adsorbed oxygen species which migrate over the surface until two charged oxygen atoms meet on adjacent sites combine and desorb as O₂ (step 4). This desorption will give rise to R₂ centre on the surface which is subsequently destroyed either by oxygen absorption or by the migration of lattice O²⁻ ions thus creating the necessary F-centres for the active adsorption of N₂O. When the surface coverage is high (*i.e.* at pressures >200 torr) the surface migration of adsorbed oxygen species and the resultant desorption is restricted and thus becomes rate controlling. At low surface coverages (*i.e.* at initial pressures less than <500 torr) the adsorption of N₂O in the reactive form appears to govern the overall rate. Whatever may be the rate controlling step, there is effective electron trapping from the catalyst or electron release to the catalyst appear to involve in the rate determining step thus justifying designating this reaction as suprafacial catalysis.

Electrical conductivity and activity :

If electron trapping is involved in the rate determining step then activation energy (E_{σ}) for electrical conduction will not bear a direct relationship with activity as free electron mobility and its

total number alone cannot decide the transfer to the adsorbing molecule but also its energy. On the other hand, if electron release to the catalyst is involved in the rate determining step then the mobility and number of the electrons, govern their transfer rather than their energy and accordingly one would expect a correlation between E_{σ} and activity. This has been experimentally verified in this investigation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Correlation Between E_{α} for N₂O Decomposition (>200 Torr) and E_{σ} for Electrical Conduction.

The results obtained by Schelz and Scheve⁴ on ZnO doped with Li₂O or Ga₂O₃ are shown in Fig. 2. This figure includes the variation of specific conductivity at 690° the activation energy for electrical conduction, the ratios of conductivities in N₂O and air, the activation energy for N₂O decom-

Fig. 2. Variation of ratio of conductivities in nitrous oxide and in air at 690°C (●), activation energy for (○) electrical conduction, logarithm of specific conductivity at 690°C (●) logarithm of rate constant at 697°C (○) and activation energy for nitrous-oxide decomposition (▼) as a function of concentration of dopant in ZnO.

position as well as the specific rate constant at 697°, as a function of dopant concentration. The data obtained by Schwab and Block⁵ as well as the data from the present work are included in this figure. The striking parallelism between the variation of specific conductivity and the activation energy for decomposition as well as the similar trends observed for variation of activation energy and specific rate constants strongly supports the conclusion that the electron transfer steps are the important ones in the reaction mechanism.

Cunningham *et al*⁶ have tried to establish that the localization of the electron is the rate determining in the decomposition reaction based upon their investigation that the conductivity of *n*-type oxides (doped ZnO catalysts) decreases in N₂O ambient and the variation is similar to what has been observed with O₂. Above all they have computed the effective charge carrier concentration in these systems and have shown that the number of N₂O molecules decomposed increases directly with the number of mobile charge carriers. The data on the titanates studied are collected in Table 3. It

was not possible to evolve a direct relationship between the electrical parameters of the systems and the activity as the titanate considered in this work contains other cations, some of which are capable of exhibiting variable valency and hence can contribute to the electrical conduction in some cases by more than one mechanism. However, the relevance of electron transfer steps have been brought out from the measurements of conductivity changes and Seebeck coefficient determinations reported in the following section.

Seebeck potential and N₂O decomposition

Assuming that one type of charge carrier predominates, the Seebeck coefficient can be written as

$$\alpha = \pm \frac{k}{e} \left[A + \ln \frac{2(2 m^* k T)^{3/2}}{h^3} \right] - \frac{k}{e} \ln n \mu e$$

where *n* and μ are the number and mobility of carriers, *m** effective mass of the carrier and A is a constant. In a reaction, where the mobility of the charge carriers at the surface is important then the change in α will be predominantly controlled by the effective mass term and will not be directly dependent on temperature while for a reaction, where the effective number of charge carriers at the surface is important then changes in α will very linearly with temperature. This is in conformity with the observations recorded in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Changes in thermo-electric power in N₂O atmosphere as a function of temperature-effect of pressure.

TABLE-3. VALUES OF THE ELECTRONIC PROPERTIES AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR N₂O DECOMPOSITION ON TITANATES

Catalyst	Values of rate constant		Values of Seebeck coefficient in vac. at T°C	Value of conductivity		
	≥200 torr (cm ^{1/2} min ⁻¹)m ⁻²	< 50 torr (min ⁻¹)m ⁻²		(in air)	(200 torr of N ₂ O)	σ ₂ /σ ₁
MgTiO ₃	5.28 × 10 ⁻⁶ (500°C)	2.02 × 10 ⁻⁶ (500°C)	-800 μV/°C (400°C)	-	-	-
MnTiO ₃	5.71 × 10 ⁻⁵ (510°C)	2.35 × 10 ⁻⁴ (510°C)	-870 μV/°C (400°C)	3.89 × 10 ⁻⁴ (350°C)	1.383 × 10 ⁻³ (350°C)	3.56
NiTiO ₃	5.29 × 10 ⁻⁴ (490°C)	2.71 × 10 ⁻³ (510°C)	-1173 μV/°C (445°C)	4.17 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.276 × 10 ⁻⁷	3.06
CaTiO ₃	8.10 × 10 ⁻⁴ (500°C)	4.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	-	8.40 × 10 ⁻¹¹	-	-
SrTiO ₃	1.28 × 10 ⁻⁴ (495°C)	6.75 × 10 ⁻⁴	-	6.17 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	1.55 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.25
BaTiO ₃	5.10 × 10 ⁻⁵ (500°C)	9.48 × 10 ⁻⁶ (500°C)	-	-	-	-

Conclusion :

If the decomposition had been an intrafacial catalysis, then one would have observed the resultant oxidation of the catalyst after the reaction and required reduction pre-treatment for restoration of activity. This has not been found experimentally. Also, the systems that can hardly undergo oxidation under these conditions promote this reaction also proves it is not an intrafacial catalysis. Further, the various correlations obtained between N₂O decomposition and other parameters like electrical conductivity, dopent concentration etc. clearly establishes that N₂O decomposition is the best example for suprafacial catalysis in many respects.

Acknowledgement

The award of research fellowship by IIT Madras to one of the authors (GNS) is gratefully acknowledged.

References :

1. To be published.
2. J. B. GOODENOUGH, *Progress in Solid State Chemistry* (Ed., H. Reiss), Vol. 5, p 230-233, 320-325, Pergamon (1971).
3. E. R. S. WINTER, *J. Catalysis*, 1969, 15, 144.
4. W. D. SCHULZ, and J. Z. SCHEVE, *Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1969, 366, 231.
5. G. M. SCHWAB, and J. BLOCK, *Z. Fur. Electrochemic.*, 1954, 58, 756.
6. J. CUNNINGHAM, J. J. KELLY, and A. L. PENNY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 1992.